

SPACE RADIATION AND HYPERVELOCITY IMPACT SHIELDING FOR LOW EARTH ORBIT SPACE STRUCTURES USING ULTRA-HIGH-MOLECULAR-WEIGHT POLYETHYLENE

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ABSTRACT

Space radiation is defined as particle radiation consisting of protons, heavy ions, and electrons. Space radiation has a catastrophic effect on satellite electronics and reduces its lifespan. It also greatly limits the performance of satellite electronics. It makes it impossible for astronauts to stay in space for long-term because of the potential of various diseases and cancer. Polyethylene is known to perform very well in space radiation shielding. In particular, ultra- high- molecular- weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) has very high mechanical performance. Meanwhile, there are millions of space debris in Earth's orbit now. These debris have hypervelocity impact of several tens of km/s depending on the orbit and thus threaten the survival of space structures. In the case of International Space Station, the concept of Whipple shield, a dual aluminum protection system, is applied to protect the astronaut from impact of space debris. In this study, space radiation shielding and hypervelocity impact performance of proposed space structure system with ultra- high- molecular- weight polyethylene is investigated. Cyclotron was used for proton irradiation test. Also, a two stage light gas gun was used for hypervelocity impact test. The UHMWPE showed better performance in space radiation shielding and hypervelocity impact than Kevlar.

1 INTRODUCTION

In early days of satellite development (1960 ~ 1980), life spans of the satellites were observed to have been reduced due to unknown reasons. Numerous factors like trapped radiation in Van Allen Belt, galactic cosmic-rays, solar wind, cosmic-rays albedo neutrons; including electrons, protons and heavy ions can degrade the performance of satellite semiconductor components as well as shorten their lifetime [1] as shown Table 1.

Spacecraft	Launch year	Problems with space radiation
GPS	1974	Bit flip errors.
Voyager-1	1977	On board clock lost by Jovian radiation. Star tracker and transistor errors.
NIMBUS-7	1978	High-energy particles caused electrical component damage and digital data channel errors.
SMM	1980	On Board Computer errors by SEE. Memory lost and C-Gyro failed by SEE.
GOES-6	1983	Loss of pulse code modulated telemetry and telemetry system performance degradation by SEE.
Telstar-401	1993	Circuit breakdown with solar flare proton.

Table 1: Effects of space radiation [2].

As a result, semiconductor devices that go up into space need to consider the effect of space radiation resulting in new performance constraints and high cost. In the 1980s and 1990s, the United States, led by NASA's Johnson Space Center and Langley Research Center, conducted researches on space environment and shielding materials, including space radiation, and accumulated research results. Cancer caused by space radiation, acute or chronic central nervous system abnormalities due to space radiation, tissue mutation due to space radiation, and other diseases such as cataract, circulatory system disease, digestive system disease and acute radiation syndrome (ARS) as a result of long - term space stay were defined as the common health threats during a manned space mission [3].

Hydrogen atoms are known to have very good space radiation shielding properties from proton and heavy ion particles. In particular, polyethylene, which has high hydrogen density, is considered as a potential material for future space radiation shielding structure. However, low mechanical properties of polyethylene at elevated temperature environment and low thermal conductivity has made it difficult for its materialization on a spacecraft panel. Development in polyethylene processing methods led to the manufacture of Ultra- High- Molecular- Weight- Polyethylene (UHMWPE) by Dyneema (Netherlands) in 1979 with superior mechanical properties than conventional polyethylene.

Recently, due to increase in MMOD (Micro Meteoroid and Orbital Debris), the effect of MMOD impact on the life of a space structure has become a serious threat as shown in Table 2.

Spacecraft	Year	Problems with MMOD
ISEE-1	1977	The detector window was punctured due to micrometeoroid impact.
KOSMOS-1275	1981	KOSMOS-1275 was broken into 200 fragments. It has been highly speculated that this was the result of a hypervelocity collision with a piece of space debris.
Mir SS	1986	A small meteorite and space debris collided on the solar panel several times and power was exhausted.
HST	1990	The whole wing suffered between 5000 and 6000 micrometeoroid impacts in four years.
Solar A	1991	The micrometeoroid collided with a thin film membrane covering its optical system.
STS-49	1992	There was a collision around the window frame.
STS-45	1992	The Space Shuttle Atlantis suffered two gouges, (1.9 in × 1.6 in and 0.4 in × 1 in), on the upper portion of the right wing leading edge.
SEDS-2	1994	The 20 km tether was severed by particle impact ending the experiment prematurely.
KOSMOS-2251/ Iridium-33	2009	Accidental explosion with each other, producing 1669 fragments.

Table 2: Effects of MMOD [2].

Types of orbital debris include payloads, rockets, some revenant space structures, propellants, and non-operational satellites with majority of these located in the low earth orbit (LEO). These debris materials typically have collision speeds in the range of 7 ~ 15 km/s. The MMOD shielding system currently in use is Whipple Shield, proposed by Fred Whipple in the 1940s, in which two aluminum plates are spaced apart at regular intervals. The phenomenon involves protection of the space structure by fragmenting the impact debris to debris clouds that occur upon impact to the front bumper, with the second wall acting as a stopping layer for these low fragments or energy debris cloud. Later Nextel and Kevlar fabric were inserted as the middle layer to improve the Whipple shield performance. Figure 1 shows Whipple shield configuration of International Space Station (ISS) Columbus module. In this study, ultra- high- molecular- weight- polyethylene (UHMWPE) is proposed as a replacement to Kevlar fiber. The space radiation shielding and hypervelocity impact performance of both UHMWPE and Kevlar fabric are compared for effective space shielding design.

Figure 1: Whipple shield configuration.

2 METHODS

2.1 Specimen characteristics

Kevlar has traditionally been used in space station for MMOD shielding. Kevlar KM2 and UHMWPE SPECTRA1000 woven fabric, which are used for bulletproof purposes, were used as specimens in this study. In this study, KM2 was used as a reference material because of its use in ISS cargo spacecraft (ATV). The specific strength and specific modulus of UHMWPE are 1.4 times than those of Kevlar as shown in Table 3. Kevlar has a material composition of C (50%), H (35%), N (7%), and O (7%). On the other hand, UHMWPE has a material composition of C (33%) and H (66%). Accordingly, UHMWPE with a high hydrogen density is expected to be more effective in shielding space radiation than Kevlar.

Material / Product name	Tensile strength (g/den) / (GPa)	Modulus (g/den) / (GPa)	Elongation (%)	Density (g/cm ³)	1 Layer area density (g/cm ²)	Denier
Kevlar / KM2	24 / 3.88	800 / 84.6	4.5	1.44	0.0188	600
UHMWP / Spectra1000	35 / 3.00	1200 / 103	3.1	0.97	0.0109	375

Table 3: Experiment material properties [4, 5].

2.2 Proton irradiation test

In this study, MC-50 Cyclotron (Korea Institute of Radiological and Medical Sciences, Seoul, Republic of Korea) was used to simulate space radiation on the ground. A proton beam with source energy of 45 MeV was generated in the Cyclotron. The beam energy decreases as the beam travels through the path of a 2 mm aluminum window, a 50 cm air layer, 2.7 mm aluminum degrader, and a remaining air layer as shown in Figure 2. As a result, 27.5 MeV energy required for the experiment was obtained. The reason for choosing the experimental energy as 27.5 MeV is to use the shielding

reference [6]. The area density of Kevlar and UHMWPE woven fabric for shielding 27.5 MeV protons was compared. The current value reading by the ion chamber can be used to determine if the proton is shielded.

Figure 1: Proton irradiation facility setup.

2.3 Impact test

Hypervelocity impact experiment was carried out using a two-stage light gas gun (Figure 2) in Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology. Impact absorption energies of 6 Kevlar (0.113 g/cm^2) and 10 UHMWPE (0.109 g/cm^2) with similar areal density were compared. The impact experiments were performed using Al 1070-T4 5.56 mm Φ sphere ($m_{\text{proj}} = 0.2509 \text{ g}$) and the reduced kinetic energy was obtained using a magnetic and a laser sensor system located before and after impact specimen. In low velocity (0.5 km/s) and hypervelocity (3.2 km/s) impact tests, the absorbed energy (E_{absorbed}) was calculated using Equation (1) and the specific absorbed energy ($E_{\text{specific absorbed}}$) using Equation (2).

$$E_{\text{absorbed}} = m_{\text{proj}} (v_{\text{initial}}^2 - v_{\text{residual}}^2) / 2 \quad (1)$$

$$E_{\text{specific absorbed}} = E_{\text{absorbed}} / \text{Areal density} \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: Two-stage light gas gun.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Proton irradiation test

The areal density of Kevlar and UHMWPE fabric, in which protons of 27.5 MeV are shielded, were obtained as shown in Figure 3.

Kevlar or UHMWPE ? layers (area density)

Figure 3: Proton irradiation test.

As the areal density increases, the current value read by the ion chamber approaches zero. The area density of the proton shield can be obtained at a current value close to zero. Table 4 shows the area density of the Kevlar and UHMWPE required for complete proton shielding. Compared to Kevlar in 27.5MeV proton shielding, it can be seen that the UHMWPE has a weight reduction effect of about 20.7% as shown in Table 4. Replacing Kevlar with UHMWPE could improve the space radiation shielding performance. The higher the proton shielding performances, the more proton energy can be reduced for the same areal density of a material. UHMWPE's high proton shielding performance makes it a likely material to be used in future manned spacecrafts.

Proton irradiation energy	Material	Number of layers	Shielded area density	Weight % over UHMWPE
27.5 MeV	Kevlar fabric	49	0.9212 g/cm ²	120.7 %
27.5 MeV	UHMWPE fabric	70	0.7630 g/cm ²	100.0 %

Table 4: Compares the proton shielding performance of 27.5 MeV.

3.2 Impact test

A similar areal density of 6 Kevlar (0.1128 g/cm²) layer case and 10 UHMWPE (0.1090 g/cm²) layer case were compared in impact test as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4: Impact test.

Impact tests were performed to measure the velocity of projectile before impact and after penetration of fabric. At low velocity impact speeds (Table 4) and hypervelocity impact speeds (Table 5), the specific absorbed energy was greater in the case of UHMWPE than that of Kevlar.

	Initial velocity	Residual velocity	E _{absorbed}	E _{Specific absorbed}
UHMWPE	0.492 km/s	0.315 km/s	0.01792 kJ	0.1638 kJ·cm ² /g
Kevlar	0.483 km/s	0.299 km/s	0.01805 kJ	0.1599 kJ·cm ² /g

Table 4: Low velocity impact test results.

	Initial velocity	Residual velocity	E _{absorbed}	E _{Specific absorbed}
UHMWPE	3.262 km/s	3.022 km/s	0.1892 kJ	1.729 kJ·cm ² /g
Kevlar	3.236 km/s	2.989 km/s	0.1929 kJ	1.708 kJ·cm ² /g

Table 5: Hypervelocity impact test results.

The specific absorption energy of UHMWPE in low velocity impact was 2.4% larger than that of Kevlar. In addition, the specific absorption energy of UHMWPE in hypervelocity impact was 1.2% larger than Kevlar. From a practical standpoint, the UHMWPE's ballistic performance in the Whipple shield will be slightly better than Kevlar. Moreover, there is a difference in the space radiation shielding performance that it makes a better material for space applications when compared with Kevlar.

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, UHMWPE woven fabric was proposed as a material to replace Kevlar to increase proton shielding performance of Whipple shield. Proton irradiation test showed that UHMWPE had higher proton shielding performance than Kevlar. In addition, impact test confirmed that UHMWPE had higher specific absorbed energy than Kevlar. Based on these results, the use of UHMWPE in the Whipple shield will have better space radiation shielding and MMOD shielding performance than the conventional space shielding structures.

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